

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF HYBRID LEARNING POLICY DURING COVID 19 IN MALANG CITY

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ABSTRACT

Due to the emergence of this virus in the field of education and causing problems in the education system in Indonesia, the Minister of Education and Culture issued regulation No. 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of Education Policies in the Emergency Period for the Spread of Corona Virus Diseases-19. The policy is asked school to implement hybrid learning, where some of the class is conducted online. This research is conducted to find out the implementation of hybrid learning policy during covid 19 in Malang city. The research method used in this study is qualitative research method. This policy was created to provide guidance to the community in carrying out educational activities. The research conducted through three implementation policy; organization, implementation and application. It is found out that education is a very important thing for the progress of a country. Even during the Covid-19 pandemic, education is required to continue even under emergency conditions. The implementation of hybrid learning policy in schools in Malang city is running effectively. However, there are several problems that can be found such as teacher that prefer to do face to face meeting and some teachers who did not familiar with technology such as zoom.

KEYWORDS

Implementation, Hybrid Learning Policy, Covid 19

INTRODUCTION

Education is basically a process of delivering diverse knowledge in the form of teaching gradually. The National Education System Law No. 20 of 2003 states that "Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, as well as the skills needed by himself, society, nation and state".

But lately in various parts of the world there is a virus pandemic called corona or better known as Covid-19 (Corona Virus Diseases 19). The spread of the pandemic is the cause of the highest death rate in various countries in the world today. Many victims died due to exposure to the virus. In fact, many medical personnel who became victims and died. This is a problem that the world must face today, in order to implement various policies, including in Indonesia itself.

Due to the emergence of this virus in the field of education and causing problems in the education system in Indonesia, the Minister of Education and Culture issued regulation No. 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of Education Policies in the Emergency Period for the Spread of Corona Virus Diseases-19. Through the Circular Letter of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 4 of 2020 (Kemendikbud, 2020) regarding the Implementation of Education Policies in the Emergency Period for the Spread of Covid-19, the Minister of Education and Culture appealed to all levels of schools, universities, and other educational institutions that teaching and learning activities take place online from their homes.

- respectively, so that the face-to-face learning process in schools is temporarily suspended. This is intended to reduce and reduce the expansion of the spread of COVID-19, so all activities that can trigger crowds and gatherings that can involve many people need to be avoided. Learning activities that were initially carried out conventionally, need to follow a new policy that has been changed by the Minister of Education and Culture, namely by implementing Distance Learning (PJJ) where the teaching and learning process is 100% online without any face to face (Maulida, 2020).

In the online learning process (online) there are several obstacles or negative impacts that are generated while implementing online learning, one of which is in terms of the quality of learning where teachers and students can initially communicate and interact directly in the classroom, but currently the interaction is limited. only in virtual space. By being faced with the current conditions, the teacher must be able to develop the learning process effectively so as not to result in a decrease in the quality of student learning and a decrease in student learning outcomes. More effective and efficient learning concepts are needed to support successful learning during this pandemic.

Hybrid learning can be an alternative learning to reduce problems in online learning that is applied in Indonesia. In general, Hybrid Learning is learning that combines face-to-face and online learning by using various learning methods that combine face-to-face meetings with online teaching to improve learning skills. Hybrid Learning can be an ideal lesson to be applied in the midst of this pandemic, because it offers two methods that are in accordance with the idea of an education system in the midst of a pandemic put forward by the Ministry of Education and Culture Nadiem Makarim. Learning activities can be done by collaborating with conventional learning in the form of face-to-face in explaining and delivering material, besides that it can shorten the duration of learning at school and can keep a distance by not interacting directly with teachers through online virtual classes. The assignment system can also be implemented online using various learning technologies.

Based on the background and the results of initial observations, the researcher wants to evaluate the implementation of Hybrid learning policy during the pandemic period of Covid-19 in Malang city, since Malang is one of the famous educational cities in Indonesia. The evaluation will determine whether the implementation of blended learning during pandemic is successful or not.

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research uses descriptive qualitative research, this research aims to understand phenomena about things that happen to the research subject, for example things experienced by actors, perceptions, motivations, actions, etc., thoroughly by means of descriptions in the form of words and language on a context.

The main research instrument this research is interview, Interviews have slight differences compared to other interviews, such as interviews on new employee admissions, new student admissions, or even in quantitative research. Thus, if using the interview technique, the data will be obtained directly more clearly by the researcher. In this interview, the researcher used the face-to-face method, by giving several questions to the informants directly. The instruments used for this interview were in the form of small notes to record the answers to the informant's questions, a tape recorder, and a camera.

This data analysis technique uses the model. The model chosen in this study is the Charles O'Jones model. Where this model explains that policy implementation is an activity that is intended to operate a program by taking into account three main activities, namely: organization, interpretation and application.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hybrid Learning is an English term which consists of two words, Hybrid and learning. Hybrid means a mixture or combination while learning is learning. Hybrid Learning is basically a combination of the advantages of learning that is carried out face-to-face and virtually. Hybrid Learning combines aspects of web/internet-based learning, video streaming, synchronous and asynchronous audio communication with traditional "face-to-face" learning (Sjukur, 2012: 4). The application of Hybrid Learning is expected that students can understand the material better and be more active in participating in learning, so as to improve student learning outcomes. Hybrid Learning is basically a combination of the advantages of learning that is carried out face to face (face to face learning) and virtually (e-learning). Online learning or e-learning in Hybrid Learning is a natural extension of traditional classroom learning that uses a face-to-face learning model (Izzudin, 2012: 5).

Organization must be supported by the existence of a flexible organization with clear and directed main tasks and supported by reliable policy implementers and have undoubted capacity in carrying out organizational tasks, so that every policy implemented will become a reality and accepted by and in the public interest. The organizations in this study are the Malang City Education Office and schools. The Malang City Education Office has provided the best service for online learning. In this case the Malang City Education Office as an intermediary from the central government to students has made good efforts in terms of education in Malang City.

From the aspect of interpretation, in this study it can be seen that interpretation provides a description of the tasks that can be carried out in order to implement the policy. For example, the education office provides directions for schools and students to implement hybrid learning. It can be seen from the education office that they are very considerate of this learning activity in order to remain obedient to the health protocol. With its organizational function, the education office provides a policy that requires schools that are ready to carry out face-to-face learning to fill out the appropriate readiness on the dapodik page, which serves to make it easier for the education office to monitor which schools are ready to carry out face-to-face learning. So, to continue to be able to monitor teaching and learning activities, schools that are ready to carry out face-to-face learning must fill out the Dapodik website, when schools are not ready, they cannot be allowed. In addition, in preventing crowds when face-to-face learning is limited, the office provides different schedules for schools that are close together, reducing crowds for both students and student introductions.

Every policy product that is carried out by an organization that is flexible and existential, and supported by interpretive capabilities described at the technical level of implementation, is therefore an absolute requirement so that the policy will be more applicable, so that the policy is not just a wishful thinking that does not materialize. in reality. In this application the interview focuses on the target of the policy, namely students and parents of students. From the results of the interview, various obstacles were faced in participating in learning activities during the Covid-19 pandemic. Various obstacles can be seen there are similarities in each student who has participated in the interview. With online learning, students feel less able to understand the material presented by the teacher, because students can only receive most of the material

from the questions given by the teacher or only read on their own with parental guidance. In addition, teachers also rarely explain the material obtained by students. In the midst of the increasing cases of Covid 19, students also continue to obey the rules given to prevent the transmission of Covid 19 which are the facilities and directions that have been given by the school. But besides that, students who took part in interviews got good grades, so this is quite a question because students who when answering interview questions got a lot of difficulties but when the exam got good scores. By using the Zoom Meeting facility with teachers to get learning materials.

In research on the implementation of hybrid learning policies during the COVID-19 pandemic, it can be seen that a policy will run well if every actor in implementing this policy cooperates with each other according to their function. This study uses a policy implementation model from Charles o Jones in which the policy implementation model is an activity intended to operate a program by paying attention to 3 main activities, including application organization and interpretation. In this case the theoretical implications are from research based on the theory used. Too based on the theory coined by Charles o Jones in which the organization, namely every implementation of the policy must be supported by the existence of a flexible organization with clear and directed main tasks and supported by reliable policy implementers and have undoubted capacity in carrying out their duties. Moreover, Thompson in Thoha (2008), stated that an organization is s a 'highly' rationalized and impersonal of a large number of specialists cooperating to achieve some announced specific objective to the organization so that every policy implemented will become a reality and be accepted by the public interest. The Malang city education office as well as schools under the Malang city education office have implemented this policy as well as possible for the creation of good education. This research is useful for providing and also enriching studies in science, especially in the theory of public policy implementation. According to Bryson (2004), strategic planning as a disciplined effort to produce fundamental decisions and actions that shape a guide what an organization (om other entity) is, what it does, and why it does it. In addition to contributing to enriching this scientific study, this research discusses the hybrid learning policies created during the covid-19 pandemic which can later be useful in the future to provide insight into the problems we face today that will be useful for future generations.

It is hoped that the next generation can take values that can be used to solve problems that occur, also the next generation can consider how to solve problems caused by things that were not previously anticipated. In addition, what can be obtained from this research, especially on the theoretical aspect, is to give influence to the city of Malang which is appointed in this study, especially in the field of education affected by COVID-19, which this research will provide input to the local government of Malang city to improve the quality of education. during the pandemic and in the non-pandemic period and also to all regions in Indonesia. Although apart from during the pandemic, Dan this can also be used as a reference in solving problems that can come at any time. This research also focuses on giving students the rights to continue to learn even in difficult times. Based on the theory used, this study uses three aspects of Jones theory. Jones (1996) stated that there are three steps to conduct public policy namely organization, application, and interpretation. This research organization is aimed at the Malang city education office and also schools under the Malang city education office which are the implementers of this policy.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research above, it can be concluded that hybrid learning policy was created to provide boundaries and ways for an activity in the community. This policy was

created to provide guidance to the community in carrying out educational activities. Education is a very important thing for the progress of a country. Even during the Covid-19 pandemic, education is required to continue even under emergency conditions. The implementation of hybrid learning policy in schools in Malang city is running effectively. However, there are several problems that can be found such as teacher that prefer to do face to face meeting and some teachers who did not familiar with technology such as zoom

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